

FAIR DO Implementation in Coscine

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Status of this Document

This is a working Document. It will be continuously enhanced. The current version should be considered to have a "beta" status".Feedback is welcome.

Other FDO KIP Documents:

- Helmholtz KIP: https://oceanrep.geomar.de/id/eprint/57942/7/2022-12_HMC-Paper_2_PID-KIP_V1.pdf (https://oceanrep.geomar.de/id/eprint/57942/7/2022-12_HMC-Paper_2_PID-KIP_V1.pdf)
- RDA Recommendation: [https://www.rd-alliance.org/system/files/RDA Recommendation on PID Kernel Information_final.pdf](https://www.rd-alliance.org/system/files/RDA%20Recommendation%20on%20PID%20Kernel%20Information_final.pdf) (https://www.rd-alliance.org/system/files/RDA%20Recommendation%20on%20PID%20Kernel%20Information_final.pdf)
- Cookbook: <https://kit-data-manager.github.io/fairdo-cookbook/> (<https://kit-data-manager.github.io/fairdo-cookbook/>)

Template

Semantic

Identifier

Cardinality

Format

Example

Implementation Details

Specification

Overview

Coscine KIP v 1.0

- `kernelInformationProfile` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#kernelinformationprofile) {height=16}
- `digitalObjectType` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjecttype) {height=16}
- `digitalObjectLocation` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocation) {height=16}
- `dateCreated` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#datecreated) {height=16}
- `contact` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#contact) ↔ {height=16}
- `license` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#license) ↔ {height=16}
- `topic` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#topic) ↔ {height=16}
- `metadataGraphLocation` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#metadatagraphlocation) 🔍 {height=16}

Candidates for Coscine KIP v 2.0

- `digitalObjectLocationAccessProtocol` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocationaccessprotocol) ↔ {height=16}
- `enforcesAccess` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#enforcesaccess) 🔍 {height=16}
- `IsPartOf` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#ispartof) 🔍 {height=16} /
`HasPart` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#haspart) 🔍 {height=16}

Fields from RDA Recommendation

`kernelInformationProfile` {height=16}

Semantic

A PID pointing to the KIP which provides the structure of this PID record.

Identifier

● Reuse: 21.T11148/076759916209e5d62bd5 (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/objects/21.T11148/076759916209e5d62bd5>)

Cardinality

1

Format / Type

PID (21.T11148/3626040cadcac1571685 (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/objects/21.T11148/3626040cadcac1571685>))

Example

21.T11148/c05c111ec05c111e

Implementation Details

All FDO-PIDs created by Coscine will use "Coscine KIP" 21.T11148/c05c111ec05c111e (PID to be defined).

digitalObjectType {height=16}

Semantic

A PID pointing to a data type in a Data Type Registry describing the object referenced by `digitalObjectLocation` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocation) {height=16}.

Identifier

 Reuse: 21.T11148/1c699a5d1b4ad3ba4956 (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/objects/21.T11148/1c699a5d1b4ad3ba4956>)

Cardinality

1

Format

PID (21.T11148/3626040cadcac1571685 (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/objects/21.T11148/3626040cadcac1571685>))

Example

21.T11148/c05c111ec05c111e

Implementation Details

All FDO-PIDs created by Coscine will be of type "Catalog (context DCAT)" 21.T11148/c05c111ec05c111e (🔴 Create PID). If DTR allows, two subtypes could be created for Project and Resource. In the future this might be extended by a user selectable type (from a list) in Coscine.

digitalObjectLocation {height=16}

Semantic

A web-resolvable pointer to the actual object described by this PID record.

Identifier

🟢 Reuse: 21.T11148/b8457812905b83046284 (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/b8457812905b83046284>)

Cardinality

1..n

Format

URL (21.T11148/e0efc41346cda4ba84ca (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/e0efc41346cda4ba84ca>))

Examples

- <https://api.coscine.de/c05c111e-6b56-44e4-a735-7a637b21b888/c05c111e-c4ac-4ca8-9466-60fdd72bd6b9/>
- <s3://coscine-s3-01.s3.fds.rwth-aachen.de:9021/c05c111e-244b-4ded-a0ac-3bf6582798df/>
- <git://git@git.rwth-aachen.de:coscine/docs/public/documentation.git>

Implementation Details

This field should be populated with **all** of the applicable

- For Projects: Full URL of the project in the project API
- For Resources: Full URL to the resource root in resources API
- For public Resources or Resources in public projects: Full URL of the backend system (e.g. S3 endpoint, URL to gitlab, ...)

dateCreated {height=16}

Semantic

The date in ISO 8601 format, when the object referenced by `digitalObjectLocation` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocation) {height=16} was initially created.

Identifier

 Reuse: 21.T11148/aafd5fb4c7222e2d950a (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/aafd5fb4c7222e2d950a>)

Cardinality

1

Format

ISO Date/Time (21.T11148/3bfb2839a6967114bc3e (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/3bfb2839a6967114bc3e>))

Example

2021-04-14T10:43:31Z

Implementation Details

Current date time when the project or resource was created in ISO format and UTC timezone.

Currently Discarded Fields from RDA Recommendation

- `digitalObjectPolicy` {height=16}: Discarded due to unclear definition. May be introduced in the future to distinguish between archived and non-archived resources.
- `etag` {height=16}: Discarded as non applicable for the collections of files referenced by Coscine.
- `dateModified` {height=16}: Discarded as non applicable for the collections of files referenced by Coscine.
- `version` {height=16}: Discarded as non applicable for the collections of files referenced by Coscine.
- `wasDerivedFrom` {height=16}: Discarded as provenance information is part of the metadata graph. A field `provenanceGraphLocation` might be introduced.
- `specializationOf` {height=16}: Discarded as provenance information is part of the

metadata graph. A field `provenanceGraphLocation` might be introduced.

- `wasRevisionOf` {height=16}: Discarded as provenance information is part of the metadata graph. A field `provenanceGraphLocation` might be introduced.
- `hadPrimarySource` {height=16}: Discarded as provenance information is part of the metadata graph. A field `provenanceGraphLocation` might be introduced.
- `wasQuotedFrom` {height=16}: Discarded as provenance information is part of the metadata graph. A field `provenanceGraphLocation` might be introduced.
- `alternateOf` {height=16}: Discarded as provenance information is part of the metadata graph. A field `provenanceGraphLocation` might be introduced.

Coscine Extensions to the RDA Recommendation

contact ↔{height=16}

Semantic

A web-resolvable pointer to an institution or a person responsible for the object referenced by `digitalObjectLocation` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocation) {height=16}.

Identifier

 Reuse: 21.T11148/1a73af9e7ae00182733b (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/1a73af9e7ae00182733b>)

Cardinality

0..n

Format

URL (21.T11148/e0efc41346cda4ba84ca (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/e0efc41346cda4ba84ca>))

Example

<https://ror.org/04xfq0f34>

Implementation Details

Link to the `pidresolve` page. Additionally, for public resources, resources in public projects and `public projects` links to all participating institutions.

license {height=16}

Semantic

URL referring to the license of the object referenced by `digitalObjectLocation` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocation) {height=16}, its modifiers (if applicable), and its version.

Identifier

 Reuse: 21.T11148/2f314c8fe5fb6a0063a8 (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/2f314c8fe5fb6a0063a8>)

Cardinality

0..n

Format

URL (21.T11148/e0efc41346cda4ba84ca (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/e0efc41346cda4ba84ca>))

Example

<https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.html>

Implementation Details

Not available in projects, from selected license in resource. Only for `public` resources, resources in `public` projects. Commonly known licenses should be mapped to spdx catalog. May link to custom license document.

topic {height=16}

Semantic

One or more topics the object referenced by `digitalObjectLocation` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocation) {height=16} is related to.

Identifier

 Reuse: 21.T11148/b415e16fbe4ca40f2270 (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/b415e16fbe4ca40f2270>)

Cardinality

1..n

Format

URL (21.T11148/e0efc41346cda4ba84ca (http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/e0efc41346cda4ba84ca))

Example

http://www.dfg.de/dfg_profil/gremien/fachkollegien/liste/index.jsp?id=409

Implementation Details

From selected discipline of project or resource. Only for public resources, resources in public projects or public projects.

metadataGraphLocation {height=16}

Semantic

A web-resolvable pointer to a metadata document for the object referenced by `digitalObjectLocation` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocation) {height=16}.

Identifier

 Create

Cardinality

1

Format

 Reuse: URL (21.T11148/e0efc41346cda4ba84ca (http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/e0efc41346cda4ba84ca))

Example

- <https://purl.org/coscine/resources/c05c111e-c4ac-4ca8-9466-60fdd72bd6b9/>
- <https://ldp.coscine.de/resources/c05c111e-c4ac-4ca8-9466-60fdd72bd6b9/>

Implementation Details

Full URL pointing to the LDP root document of the resource or project created
→ link auf LDP URL (<https://coscine.de/ldp/{GUID}/> (<https://coscine.de/ldp/%7BGUID%7D/>),
<https://purl.org/coscine/resources/c05c111e-c4ac-4ca8-9466-60fdd72bd6b9/> (<https://purl.org/coscine/resources/c05c111e-c4ac-4ca8-9466-60fdd72bd6b9/>))

digitalObjectLocationAccessProtocol {height=16}

Semantic

Additional information which can be used by an access client for accessing
`digitalObjectLocation` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocation) {height=16}.

Identifier

 Reuse: 21.T11148/dcd4e99d26a00b8132f8 (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/dcd4e99d26a00b8132f8>)

Cardinality

0..n

Format

String (21.T11148/3df63b7acb0522da685d (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/3df63b7acb0522da685d>))

Example

- {"protocol":"HTTP", "url":"text/html"}

Implementation Details

 Debatable if useful since it is expected that multiple `digitalObjectLocation` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocation) {height=16} exist and correspondig values cannot be properly assigned.

enforcesAccess {height=16}

Semantic

Describes whether access policies are enforced for the object referenced by
`digitalObjectLocation` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocation) {height=16}.

Identifier

 Reuse: [21.T11148/fcfcf6aac968a2ed84d0](http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/fcfcf6aac968a2ed84d0) (http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/#objects/21.T11148/fcfcf6aac968a2ed84d0)

Cardinality

1

Format

Booleen

Example

true

Implementation Details

⚠ It needs to be checked if the field is applicable for the purpose! For FDOs created by Coscine this is always true . An additional property like visibility might be needed to distinguish between publicly available and restricted access resources. Alternative could be to define an accessPolicy or acl that also includes more detailed information like public read, restricted write .

isPartOf {height=16}

Semantic

Describes that the object referenced by digitalObjectLocation (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocation) {height=16} is part of a higher level catalog.

Inverse of hasPart (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#haspart)

{height=16}

Identifier

 Create

Cardinality

0..n

Format

 Reuse: PID (21.T11148/3626040cadcac1571685 (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/objects/21.T11148/3626040cadcac1571685>))

Example

21.11102/c05c111e-244b-4ded-a0ac-3bf6582798df

Implementation Details

 Note: `isPartOf` is borrowed from Data Cite. In the context of coscine it should be checked if borrowing `dcat:catalog` or `dcat:resource` is more suitable.

PIDs of the project that a resource is part of. Only for `public` resources or resources in `public` projects.

hasPart {height=16}

Semantic

Describes that the object referenced by `digitalObjectLocation` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#digitalobjectlocation) {height=16} consists of lower level catalogs or datasets. Inverse of `isPartOf` (https://pad.otc.coscine.dev/XnZ3R4ycQei3s_YzJivHcA?view#ispartof)

 {height=16}

Identifier

 Create

Cardinality

0..n

Format

 Reuse: PID (21.T11148/3626040cadcac1571685 (<http://dtr-test.pidconsortium.eu/objects/21.T11148/3626040cadcac1571685>))

Example

21.11102/c05c111e-244b-4ded-a0ac-3bf6582798df

Implementation Details

△ Note: `hasPart` is borrowed from Data Cite. In the context of cosine it should be checked if borrowing `dcat:catalog` or `dcat:resource` is more suitable.

PIDs of resources part of a project. Only for `public` projects.

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